

EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES: CURING KINETICS AND PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Thermoset nanocomposites based on epoxy resins, unsaturated polyester resins, vinylester resins, polyurethane resins, and nano-layered silicates have been extensively studied during the last few years. Scientists have proven that the properties of the thermoset polymers have been significantly improved, including the mechanical properties, the barrier behavior, the thermal stability and the flame resistance, etc. However, performance of nanocomposites is strongly dependent on dispersion of the nanoclays in the epoxy matrix and at the same time the interface interaction between the nano-particles and the polymer matrix. Formation of thermoset always involves curing reactions, therefore, performance of thermoset nanocomposites is also determined by the crosslink structures. It has been identified that the presence of organo-clays has affected the curing reaction, however, this effect on the curing kinetics and performance has not been fully considered so far.

In order to overcome this lack of knowledge, we have undertaken a study of a number of samples of epoxy nanocomposites prepared by different procedures, ingredients, and conditions. The techniques used include differential scanning calorimetry, infrared spectroscopy, viscosity, X-ray diffraction analysis and mechanical test. The results have shown that, depending on the curing temperature, the type of curing agent, and the type and concentration of organo-nanoclays, the curing kinetics have been affected differently, impacting on the obtained crosslink network as reflected in the transition temperatures and mechanical properties of the nanocomposites. Finally, glass fiber reinforced-nanocomposites have been prepared and their performance has also been evaluated.

Key words: nanocomposites, epoxy, curing, mechanical properties, glass transition temperature.

INTRODUCTION

The dispersion of organo-nanoclay in the polymer matrix is the most important issue in the formation of nanocomposites because it determines the reinforcing efficiency of the organo-nanoclay in the matrix and thus the performance and properties of the resulting product. Dispersion of nanoclay into the polymer matrix can take place by either a peel or a shear mechanism. According to the peel

mechanism, polymer molecules diffuse into the clay galleries through either physical or chemical attraction between the polymer molecule and the nanoclay surface. As a result, the gallery distance increases while at the same time the attraction between the clay platelets decreases, and finally the clay platelets are peeled off from each other. In the shear mechanism, on the other hand, mechanical forces shear off the nanoclay aggregates and finally break them into smaller pieces. Temperature plays an important role in the dispersion of the nanoclay, whether the peel or the shear mechanism applies. Temperature has a positive effect on the diffusion process, which is favourable to dispersion by peel control. However, it also reduces the viscosity of the polymer, which is unfavourable to dispersion by shear control. The chemical affinity between organo-clay and polymer plays a determining role in the peel process because it controls the diffusion process, but it does not have the same impact on the shear process. The formation of epoxy nanocomposites also follows these principles. However, for low viscosity systems like epoxy, the shear effect does not have a great impact on the dispersion at high temperature. It is important to stress that, depending on the chemistry of the organo-nanoclay and the temperature, homopolymerization of epoxy groups initiated by organo-nanoclay may occur during the dispersion step. As a result, the physical and chemical properties of the epoxy matrix (for example, viscosity and flowability, crosslink structure, etc.) may change in an undesired manner, and explosion could occur as a result of overheating arising from the high heat enthalpy of this reaction. This means that this reaction must be avoided in the preparation of epoxy nanocomposites.

Because of this problem, it has been recommended that the preparation of epoxy nanocomposites be done at modest temperatures, not higher than 90°C [1-9]. As stated above, because of the possibility of homopolymerization, depending on the chemistry of the onium compound used to treat the nanoclay, the optimum mixing temperature may not be the same for every system. Since mixing at low temperature results in low dispersion efficiency and is time-consuming, it is important to define an upper temperature limit for the mixing process for each organo-nanoclay.

The present work aims to understand the effect of the chemistry of the organo-nanoclay, mixing temperature, and mixing time on the homopolymerization of epoxy in order to determine the temperature limit for the preparation of epoxy nanocomposites. In addition, it also helps us to control the curing of the nanocomposites with hardener in the later steps. This on-going work concentrates on the effects of these parameters on the exfoliation and the barrier and mechanical properties of the nanocomposites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The two most widely recommended organo-nanoclays for epoxy resins were chosen for study; they differ in the chemistry of the onium ion. The first one is Cloisite 30B, which was kindly supplied by Southern Clay Products, Inc., and the second one is Nanomer I30E as obtained from Nanocor, Inc. Cloisite 30B consists of montmorillonite treated with a methyl bis-2-hydroxyethyl tallow quaternary amine, while Nanomer I30E consists of montmorillonite treated with a primary amine based on the octadecyl group.

The resin and hardener selected for this study were Shell Epon 828 and Shell Epicure 3046, respectively. This is one of the most popular systems for a low curing temperature process, recommended for production of a large range of semi-rigid products including coatings, adhesives, and composites.

Preparation of the Nanocomposites

The nanoclay content in the epoxy was varied between 1 and 4 wt%. The nanoclay was dispersed directly into the epoxy matrix by means of mixing at various temperatures between 100 and 140°C for different periods of time ranging between 0.5 and 4 h. Table 1 describes the samples prepared. Finally, the glass fiber composites were prepared from the nanocomposite matrix 30B-2-140-240 with the glass fiber loading of 50 wt% by hand lay-up method.

Characterization of the Nanocomposites

The samples were analyzed by Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The FT-IR spectra were acquired on a Nicolet Magna 860 instrument with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} by means of the attenuated total reflection (ATR) technique. The DSC curves were measured on a Perkin-Elmer DSC7 instrument under nitrogen atmosphere. For non-isothermal scans, the sample was heated from 0°C to 250°C at different heating rates between 2 and $20^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (“first scan”) to follow the chemical reaction happening in this temperature range. Then it was cooled to 20°C at $20^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to minimize the relaxation in the second heating scan. Finally it was reheated to 220°C at $20^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (“second scan”) in order to determine the glass transition temperature (T_g) and the post-curing reaction if any. The onset temperature of the curing peak in the first scan was used to choose the curing temperature for the study of curing under isothermal conditions. To evaluate the dispersion of the nanoclays in the polymer matrix, X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained from the surface of the samples with a Scintag X2 Powder X-ray Diffractometer with CuK α radiation.

The mechanical properties of the epoxy nanocomposites were determined according to ASTM D638-99. All samples were tested at room temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As it has been reported in our previous study [10], the Cloisite 30B is quite inert with epoxy matrix at temperature up to 250°C while the Nanomer I30E can catalyze for the homopolymerization of the epoxy resin, depending on the temperature. Figure 1 shows that the DSC curves of I30E samples prepared at 100°C remained unchanged up to 240 min mixing time, while the exothermic peak of the mixtures prepared at 140°C showed a dramatic decrease after only 150 min (Fig. 2a). The second DSC scan (Fig. 2b) has confirmed the homopolymerization reaction, which has taken place in the first scan to form a solid epoxy with high glass transition temperature (T_g) above 100°C . However, no significant difference on the T_g between these samples can be observed. With the Cloisite 30B, all the mixtures with epoxy showed no significant increase in viscosity even at high mixing temperature of 140°C and long mixing times (up to 4 h). In the case of the Nanomer I30E, however, the situation was different. Although there was no noticeable increase in the viscosity for samples mixed at 100°C , substantial changes were observed at 140°C (Fig. 3). The increase in viscosity is due to polymerization of the epoxy groups during the preparation as discussed earlier. By comparison of the area of the exothermic curing peak with that of a sample mixed very briefly, the degree of polymerization achieved during mixing can be easily evaluated, and the results are given in Figure 3. An excellent correlation between the increase in viscosity and the level of polymerization is observed. In the case of the 30B samples, no significant changes were seen in any of the DSC curves, indicating that no polymerization took place.

In order to verify the nature of the reaction, FT-IR analysis was used. Figure 4 compares the spectra of the uncured material and the product from the first DSC scan. The most significant change is the disappearance of the epoxide ring band at 915 cm^{-1} upon curing. This is accompanied by the growth of a broad band around $1170\text{--}960\text{ cm}^{-1}$ that can be assigned to stretching of the C–O–C ether linkages formed by reaction of the epoxide rings. The spectrum thus indicates that the exothermic peak in the DSC curve of the first scan can be assigned to the homopolymerization of the epoxy groups initiated by the onium ion of the organo-nanoclay. It was found that the commercial clay I30E contains some unbound onium ions. This raises the question as to whether the initiation of the reaction is due to the onium ion bound on the nanoclay surface or to the unbound onium ion. In order to check this, the clay I30E was purified by washing it several times with hot deionized water. The purified product behaved in a similar manner to the unpurified one, indicating that the bound onium ion also plays a catalyst role for the homopolymerization of the epoxy.

X-ray diffraction analysis has also indicated that preparation of the nanocomposites at high temperature of 140°C has accelerated the diffusion of the polymer into the clay galleries, resulting fully exfoliation. While the one prepared at lower temperature of 100°C the nanoclays are well intercalated but not exfoliated. As shown in Figure 5, for the one prepared at 140°C no peak can be observe while fore the one prepared at lower temperature the clay peak remained but shifted to the left, indicating the increase of the gallery distance to 3.6nm.

Mechanical properties of the nanocomposites are given in Figures 6a & 6b. The results indicate that the increase of nanoclay loading increased the tensile strength while it decreased the ductility of the nanocomposites. In Figure 6a also demonstrated that the higher the mixing temperature the better the tensile strength. It can be explained by the improvement of dispersion and interface interaction at high temperature as discussed earlier. The tensile, flexural and shear properties of the glass fiber composites prepared from the neat epoxy matrix and the nanocomposite matrix (30B-2-140-240) have also been evaluated. However, no significant difference between can be observed since these composites properties are mainly governed by the fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that:

(1) Organo-clay treated with primary amine (Nanomer I30E) can play a role as a catalyst for the homopolymerization of the epoxy resin, whereas organo-clay treated with quaternary amine (Cloisite 30B) does not do so.

(2) With Cloisite 30B, mixing can be done up to 140°C with negligible risk of polymerization. With Nanomer I30E, mixing at higher temperatures must be carefully controlled; at 140°C the limit is one hour.

(3) Since organo-nanoclay treated with primary amine can promote the polymerization of epoxy groups, it is important to take this reaction into account in developing products and processes designed for high-temperature curing and involving mixtures of epoxy resin, nanoclay, and various types of hardeners.

(4) Mixing temperatures and curing temperature have significant effect on the nanocomposite performance because they both control the dispersion of the nanoclay and at the same time the chemistry of the interface and the cured epoxy network.

REFERENCES

1. P. B. Messersmith and E. P. Giannelis, Chem.Mater., 1994, **6**, 1719-1725.
2. T. Lan, P. D. Kaviratana, and T. J. Pinnavaia, J.Phys.ChemSolids, 1996, **57**, 1005-1010.
3. J. M. Brown, D. Curliss, and R. A. Vaia, Chem.Mater., 2000, **12**, 3376-3384.
4. Lü Jiankun, Ke Yucai, Qi Zongneng, and Yi Xiao-Su, J.Polym.Sci., Polym.Phys., 2001, **39**, 115-120.
5. A. S. Zerda and A. J. Lesser, J.Polym.Sci., Polym.Phys., 2001, **39**, 1137-1146.
6. P. Butzloff, N. A. D'Souza, T. D. Golden, and D. Garrett, Polym.Eng.Sci., 2001, **41**, 1794.
7. X. Kornmann, H. Lindberg, and L. A. Berglund, Polymer, 2001, **42**, 4493-4499.
8. X. Kornmann, H. Lindberg, and L. A. Berglund, Polymer, 2001, **42**, 1303-1310.
9. I.-J. Chin, T. Thurn-Albrecht, H.-C. Kim, T. P. Russell, and J.Wang, Polymer, 2001, **42**, 5947-5952.

10. M-T. Ton-That, K. C. Cole, S. V. Hoa, and D. Shen, “Effect of Temperature on the Preparation of Epoxy Nanocomposites with Nanoclays”, Proc. Fourth Joint Canada-Japan Workshop on Composites, Vancouver BC, Canada, Sept. 19-21, 2002, pp. 491-499.

Table 1 – Description of Samples

Sample	Mixing temp. (°C)	Mixing time (min)	Clay type	Clay (wt%)
30B-4-100-30	100	30	30B	4
30B-4-100-60	100	60	30B	4
30B-4-100-240	100	240	30B	4
30B-4-140-30	140	30	30B	4
30B-4-140-60	140	60	30B	4
30B-4-140-240	140	240	30B	4
I30E-4-100-30	100	30	I30E	4
I30E-4-100-60	100	60	I30E	4
I30E-4-100-240	100	240	I30E	4
I30E-4-140-30	140	30	I30E	4
I30E-4-140-60	140	60	I30E	4
I30E-4-140-150	140	150	I30E	4

Figure 1 –DSC curves of nanocomposite samples prepared at 100°C.

a)

(b)

Figure 2 – DSC curves of nanocomposite samples prepared at 140°C: (a) the first scans at 10°C·min⁻¹; (b) the second scans at 20°C·min⁻¹.

Figure 3 – Relative viscosity and level of polymerization for mixtures of clays 30B and I30E with epoxy as a function of mixing time at 140°C.

Figure 4 – FT-IR spectra of the I30E nanocomposite sample before (red, below) and after (blue, above) the first DSC scan.

Figure 5 – X-ray spectra of the I30E and its nanocomposites.

a)

b)

Figure 6 – Tensile stress (a) and ductility (b) of the nanocomposites.